

Matrix Completion in Causal Panel Models*

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Abstract

We develop an inference framework for *matrix completion* (MC) when outcomes are *missing not at random* (MNAR), a setting that arises naturally in causal panel data under the potential outcomes paradigm—only one of two potential outcomes is observed for each unit-time pair. Our approach leverages (i) a low-rank structure for potential outcome matrices and (ii) block or staggered adoption patterns that enable the construction of *submatrices* with small missing fractions. We estimate via nuclear-norm penalization within submatrices, which yields a tight element-wise error bound, and debias using a rank-constrained projection, which gives asymptotically valid inference of each element. The framework delivers *heterogeneous, unit-time-specific* treatment effects and improves upon existing methods in convergence rate and signal-to-noise requirements.

Keywords: Matrix completion; MNAR; Causal panel data; Low-rank models; Nuclear-norm penalization; Heterogeneous treatment effects.

1 Introduction

Matrix completion (MC) seeks to recover missing entries of a partially observed matrix. In causal inference with panel data, MC naturally appears because potential outcomes are only partially observed: for each unit $i \in [N]$ and time $t \in [T]$, we observe $y_{it} = w_{it}y_{it}^{(1)} + (1 - w_{it})y_{it}^{(0)}$, where $w_{it} \in \{0, 1\}$ denotes treatment. In observational data, this induces *missing-not-at-random* (MNAR) patterns tightly coupled with the underlying outcomes. Standard MC methods typically rely on missing-at-random (MAR) assumptions and may be invalid in this setting.

We propose an MNAR-aware MC framework tailored to causal panels. The key ingredients are: (i) a low-rank structure capturing stable cross-sectional and temporal patterns, and (ii) a *submatrix* strategy that exploits block or staggered adoption patterns to ensure small missing fractions. A debiasing step yields valid inference for *heterogeneous, unit-time* treatment effects.

2 Setup and Notation

Let $Y^{(d)} = M^{(d)} + E$, $d \in \{0, 1\}$ denote $N \times T$ potential outcome matrices with $\text{rank}(M^{(d)}) = r_d \ll \min(N, T)$, where we write $M^{(d)} = \Lambda^{(d)}F^{(d)\top}$ with unit- and time-specific factors. Here, E is the noise matrix. We observe

$$y_{it} = \sum_{d=0}^1 y_{it}^{(d)} \mathbf{1}\{w_{it} = d\}, \quad w_{it} \in \{0, 1\},$$

*This is an extended abstract based on (Choi and Yuan (2024)) with some additional contents regarding the estimation of the potential outcome of treated situation.

where w_{it} may depend on latent structures in $M^{(d)}$. We allow dependence in $W = (w_{it})$ consistent with block or staggered adoption. Noise entries are sub-Gaussian with variance σ^2 .

Our inferential targets include:

- Individual treatment effect $\tau_{it} = m_{it}^{(1)} - m_{it}^{(0)}$;
- Group averages over units $G \subseteq [N]$ or calendar/event-time windows;
- Dynamic profiles of cross-sectional averages.

3 Identification via Low-Rank Structure and Submatrices

When missingness is MNAR, global concentration needed for nuclear-norm penalization can fail if the missing fraction is large. Our remedy is to partition missing entries into L groups and, for each group, construct a submatrix with a small missing portion (e.g., by leveraging pretreatment periods and never-treated units). For instance, for the missing entries at the time t_o , we can construct the submatrices as described in Figure 1. On such submatrices, nuclear-norm penalization consistently recovers $M^{(d)}$ under some incoherence and signal-to-noise conditions.

Figure 1: How to construct the submatrix: We divide the missing entries at t_o into L groups. For each $1 \leq l \leq L$, we estimate the entries in G_l using the nuclear norm penalized estimation on the submatrix $Y_l^{(0)}$ after making the submatrix $Y_l^{(0)}$ as described in the right panel.

Informally, in block adoption with N_0 control units and T_0 pretreatment periods, the estimator achieves

$$\left\| \widetilde{M}^{(0)} - M^{(0)} \right\|_{\infty} = O_{\mathbb{P}} \left(N_0^{-1/2} + T_0^{-1/2} \right),$$

improving upon existing MNAR-oriented bounds in related work (e.g., Athey et al. (2021); Agarwal et al. (2023)). Similar rates hold in staggered adoption.

4 Estimation

For $d = 0$, denote by $\Omega_l^{(0)}$ the observation indicator matrix for $Y_l^{(0)}$ where $1 \leq l \leq L$ is the index for the submatrices. On each submatrix, we solve

$$\widetilde{M}_l^{(0)} = \arg \min_{A \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times T}} \left\| \Omega_l^{(0)} \circ (Y_l^{(0)} - A) \right\|_{\text{F}}^2 + \lambda_l \|A\|_*,$$

and then apply a rank- r_d projection (hard-thresholding) to debias:

$$\widehat{M}_l^{(0)} = \text{Proj}_{r_0} \left(\Omega_l^{(0)} \circ Y_l^{(0)} + \Omega_l^{(0),c} \circ \widetilde{M}_l^{(0)} \right).$$

In the case of $d = 1$, since we focus on the treatment effect on the treated, we can always observe $y_{it}^{(1)}$. To denoise and estimate the low-rank part $m_{it}^{(1)}$, we apply the spectral method or the nuclear norm penalized estimator to the fully observed submatrix of $y_{it}^{(1)}$ as described in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Estimation of $y_{it}^{(1)}$: We apply the spectral method or the nuclear norm penalized estimator to the red matrix.

If the number of treated periods (or that of the treated units) is small, we consider the model having the same λ_i across the potential situation d such that

$$y_{it}^{(d)} = \lambda_i^\top f_t^{(d)} + \epsilon_{it},$$

and overcome the problem of the small sample size of treated observations by combining the observations of $Y^{(0)}$ and $Y^{(1)}$ as described in Figure 3. In addition, with control variables x_{it} , we first estimate β in an interactive fixed-effects regression on pretreatment observations and then run the above steps on residualized outcomes $\tilde{y}_{it}^{(d)} = y_{it}^{(d)} - x_{it}^\top \hat{\beta}$.

Figure 3: Estimation of $y_{it}^{(1)}$: We can combine $Y^{(0)}$ of the pre-treatment period and $Y^{(1)}$ of the treatment period horizontally since they share the same λ_i . Then, we estimate $y_{it}^{(1)}$ of interest using the spectral method on the red matrix.

5 Inference

For averages such as $|G|^{-1} \sum_{i \in G} m_{it_0}^{(0)}$ where any $G \in [N]$, we obtain

$$V_G^{-1/2} \left(\frac{1}{|G|} \sum_{i \in G} \hat{m}_{it_0}^{(0)} - \frac{1}{|G|} \sum_{i \in G} m_{it_0}^{(0)} \right) \xrightarrow{d} \mathcal{N}(0, 1),$$

with V_G depending on singular vectors of $M^{(0)}$ and σ^2 . In addition, the inference for $m_{it}^{(1)}$ follows from the typical assertion of the factor model estimation.

Figure 4: Staggered adoption case: For the missing entries in M^* , by combining four red matrices in the left panel, we construct a block missing matrix as described in the right panel. Then, we apply the method for the block missing case on the right panel.

6 Comparison to Related Approaches

Typical two-way fixed effects estimation may be inconsistent under heterogeneous TEs with staggered adoption, and DiD extensions typically target average treatment effects on the treated (ATT). Synthetic control and matching emphasize either cross-sectional or temporal stability while our low-rank approach exploits both directions. Relative to prior MC work addressing MNAR, our submatrix strategy achieves sharper sup-norm rates and weaker SNR requirements (e.g., Athey et al. (2021); Agarwal et al. (2023); Bai and Ng (2021)).

7 Extensions

The framework extends to multiple treatments by sharing unit factors (λ_i) across potential situations as described in Figure 5. It is also applicable to ranking/choice settings via low-rank approximations to link functions, with MNAR patterns arising from selective comparisons.

Figure 5: Multiple treatments case: We can combine $Y^{(0)}$ of the pre-treatment period and $Y^{(d)}$ of the treatment period horizontally since they share the same λ_i . Then, we estimate $y_{it}^{(d)}$ of interest using the block matrix in the right panel.

8 Conclusion

We introduce an MNAR-aware matrix completion method for causal panels that (i) attains favorable sup-norm rates via submatrices, (ii) yields valid inference after debiasing, and (iii) uncovers heterogeneous, dynamic treatment effects.

References

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